

Supplemental Material

Meta-modeling for Virtual Bioequivalence Assesments Using PBPK Models

Frederic Y. Bois *et al.*

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Abbreviations

AUC	Area under the (time vs. concentration) curve
CP	Continuous phase
CQA	Critical quality attribute
GMR	Geometric means' ratio
ICL	Immune cell layer
LAI	Long-acting injectable
ODE	ordinary differential equation
PBPK	Physiologically-based pharmacokinetic
PK	Pharmacokinetic
PP	Paliperidone palmitate
PSD	Particle size distribution
VBE	Virtual bioequivalence

Meta-model development

The calculation of type 1 error requires to first know at which value of the CQA(s), here mean particle radius, the C_{max} and AUC test over reference GMRs are their acceptability limits (0.8 or 1.25) for bioequivalence. With our model, this cannot be obtained by mathematical inversion, but it can be obtained numerically by simulations. For this, we computed GMRs for various values of a hypothetical test formulation particle radius, making sure that the bounds 0.8 and 1.25 were bracketed by our estimates. Radius values tried were: 1.8, 2, 2.6, 4.6357 (which is also the mean radius of the reference formulation particle), 4.8375, 5.5, 6.7, 6.23, 7.1 and 7.5 μm . We then fitted a model to the relationship between GMRs and particle radius and used that model to estimate the “boundary” value for radius. It turned out that the relationship between radius and the logarithm of GMR is simply linear, so we used a linear regression model. Therefore, the “boundary” value for radius was obtained using the following pseudo code:

1. For N reference subjects {
2. Run a PBPK simulation of PK profile, without measurement error
3. Compute and record $\log(C_{max})$ for that reference subject
- }
4. Compute means and variances of $\log(C_{max})$ for reference group
5. For M values of test formulation particle mean radius {
6. For N test subjects {
7. Run a PBPK simulations of PK profile, without measurement error
8. Compute and record $\log(C_{max})$ and $\log(AUC)$ for that test subject
- }
9. Compute the means and variances of $\log(C_{max})$ and $\log(AUC)$ for test group M
10. Compute $C_{max} \log(GMR) = \text{mean of } \log(C_{max}) \text{ test minus mean of } \log(C_{max}) \text{ ref}$
11. Compute $AUC \log(GMR) = \text{mean of } \log(AUC) \text{ test minus mean of } \log(AUC) \text{ ref}$
12. Compute variance of $C_{max} \log(GMR) =$
13. $(\text{variance of } \log(C_{max}) \text{ test} + \text{variance of } \log(C_{max}) \text{ ref}) / N$
14. Compute variance of $AUC \log(GMR) =$
15. $(\text{variance of } \log(AUC) \text{ test} + \text{variance of } \log(AUC) \text{ ref}) / N$
- }
16. Estimate the parameters of a linear regression of $C_{max} \log(GMR)$ on radius by weighted least-squares
17. Estimate the parameters of a linear regression of $AUC \log(GMR)$ on radius by weighted least-squares
18. Compute best estimates of the radii at which the C_{max} and AUC regression lines cross GMR values 0.8 and 1.25
19. Take the lowest of the two radii as value at which type 1 error should be estimated
20. Use the power calculation code above to compute the probability of declaring BE for a test formulation with that mean particle radius value
21. End.

Some comments and precisions on the above script and procedure:

- At step 1, the number of subjects, N , was set to 2500 for each group.
- Measurement error was not added to the predicted concentrations because we aim to estimate the exact relationship between GMRs and radii, so adding noise would not help with that. Measurement noise would be lognormal and would therefore lead to normal, symmetrical, random deviations of C_{max} and AUC GMRs, per standard hypotheses on their distribution.
- Steps 16 and 17: Weighting least-squares by inverse variances makes little difference but log GMRs estimates' variances do increase with radius (see Error: Reference source not found) so that such weighting is preferable.
- Steps 16 and 17: Regressing the logarithm of GMR on the logarithm of radius or regressing the GMRs themselves lead to slightly different results, but: i. using the logarithm of GMR leads to normal residuals, compatible with the basic assumptions of least-square estimation; ii. it gives a slightly better fit; iii. the range of radii and GMR values is rather small and differences between logarithms and natural values regressions do not differ significantly. Overall, the best model is obtained by linear regression of the logarithm of GMRs on radius.
- At step 19, For the lower bioequivalence bound (0.8) of GMR, the C_{max} regression gave the lowest (most conservative and likely to overestimate type 1 error) estimate of mean particle radius. That was radius was chosen for the type 1 error estimation (step 20).

The following results were obtained for the regression of GMRs on mean particle radius. Figure 2 shows that the relationship between GMR and mean particle radius is very well approximated by a log-linear relationship for both C_{max} and AUC . Error: Reference source not found shows that GMR variances increase with particle radius, supporting the use of a weighted least-square regression.

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Figure 1: Regressions for For GMR, as in paper 2.

Figure 2: Relationships between the GMRs estimates (on a log-scale, with 2500 subjects for both test and reference) and test formulation mean radius for C_{max} (left panel) and AUC (right panel). The vertical bar for each point spans the 95% confidence interval for the GMR. The bioequivalence limits are indicated by horizontal dotted lines. The vertical green lines indicate at which radius the regression line crosses those limits. The green rectangle is therefore a representation of theoretical safe.

C and R codes

Meta-model_power_C_code_V1.c

```
/* Description: Calculate various forms of power of VBE trials with  
a meta-model coded in C.  
V1: Use the regression meta-model obtained by sensitivity analysis.  
*/
```

```
#include <R.h>  
#include <math.h>
```

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```
#include <assert.h>
#include <stdio.h>

//-----

#define GMR_intercept_mean 1.755453
#define GMR_slope_mean -0.4976173
#define GMR_intercept_SE 0.01137538
#define GMR_slope_SE 0.007331575

#define Var_intercept_mean -1.538521
#define Var_slope_mean 0.164718
#define Var_intercept_SE 0.009377961
#define Var_slope_SE 0.001731034

#define SEED_DEFAULT 314159265.3589793
#define SEED_MIN 1.0
#define SEED_MAX 2147483646.0

static int vbSwitchGauss = FALSE; /* Flag to reset switchG in NormalRandom */

typedef struct tagRANDREC {
    double seed;
} RANDREC, *PRANDREC;

static int vbNoSeed = TRUE; /* Flag to prevent use without seed */
static int vbNotInitd = TRUE; /* Flag to prevent use without initing */
static RANDREC vRandRec; /* Global random information shared by */
/* all random number functions */

//-----
void SetSeed (double dSeed)
{
    int bCorrected = 0;

    if (dSeed == 0.0) {
        dSeed = SEED_DEFAULT;
        bCorrected++;
    }

    if (dSeed < 0)
        dSeed = -dSeed; /* Don't announce this correction */

    if (dSeed < SEED_MIN) {
        dSeed = SEED_MIN + (dSeed/SEED_MIN) / (SEED_MAX-SEED_MIN);
        bCorrected++;
    }

    if (dSeed > SEED_MAX) {
        dSeed = SEED_MIN + (SEED_MAX/dSeed) / (SEED_MAX-SEED_MIN);
        bCorrected++;
    }

    assert ((/* Invalid Seed */ dSeed >= SEED_MIN && dSeed <= SEED_MAX));

    /* Assign valid seed */

    if (bCorrected)
        printf ("SetSeed(): corrected out of range random number seed\n"
            "Seed must lie in the range [%g, %g]\n"
            "New seed --> %g\n", SEED_MIN, SEED_MAX, dSeed);

    vRandRec.seed = dSeed;
    vbNoSeed = FALSE; /* Flag that seed has been set */
    vbSwitchGauss = FALSE; /* Force a reset of the normal variate sampler */
} /* SetSeed */
```

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```
//-----  
double Randoms (void)  
{  
#define a 16807.0  
#define m 2147483647.0  
#define q 127773.0 /* m Div a */  
#define r 2836.0 /* m Mod a */  
  
double hi, test;  
  
if (vbNoSeed)  
SetSeed (SEED_DEFAULT);  
  
hi = (long)(vRandRec.seed / q);  
test = a * (vRandRec.seed - q * hi) - r * hi;  
  
if (test > 0.0)  
vRandRec.seed = test;  
else  
vRandRec.seed = test + m;  
  
return (vRandRec.seed / m);  
  
#undef a  
#undef m  
#undef q  
#undef r  
} /* Randoms */  
  
//-----  
void InitRandom (int rank, double dSeed, int bWarmUp)  
{  
long i;  
  
/* Prevent nuking user's seed if not initd */  
if (vbNoSeed || dSeed != SEED_DEFAULT)  
SetSeed(dSeed);  
  
if (bWarmUp) {  
/* Warm up generator */  
for (i = 0; i < 50; i++) (void) Randoms();  
  
vbNotInitd = FALSE; /* Flag as initialized */  
}  
} /* InitRandom */  
  
//-----  
double NormalRandom (double dMean, double dSD)  
{  
double dRacine, dTemp1, dTemp2, dTemp3;  
static double memGauss;  
  
if (vbSwitchGauss) { /* used stored variate */  
vbSwitchGauss = FALSE;  
return (dMean + dSD * memGauss);  
}  
  
do {  
dTemp1 = 2 * Randoms() - 1;  
dTemp2 = 2 * Randoms() - 1;  
dRacine = dTemp1 * dTemp1 + dTemp2 * dTemp2;  
} while ((dRacine >= 1) || (dRacine == 0));  
  
dTemp3 = sqrt(-2 * log(dRacine) / dRacine);  
vbSwitchGauss = TRUE;  
}
```

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```

    memGauss = dTemp1 * dTemp3;
    return (dMean + dSD * (dTemp2 * dTemp3));
} /* NormalRandom */

//-----
double LogNormalRandom (double dMeanLog, double dSDLog)
{
    return exp( NormalRandom (dMeanLog, dSDLog));
} /* LogNormalRandom */

//-----
// Student t distribution code

// Generate the t distribution quantile table in R with
// x=rep(0, 10000); for (i in 2:10000) { x[i] = qt(0.95, i)}
// write.csv(x, file="t_0.95_quantiles.csv", row.names=F)
// plot(x, log="xy")
// uu = 2:10000
// lines(uu, 2.76*exp(exp(-1.4*log(uu)^0.8))-1.11)
// accurate at 1e-4 for df=10000, precision increases by one order of magnitude for
each order of magnitude of ndf
#define table_size 10000
double qt(double P, int ndf)
{
    static int bInited = 0;
    static double qtable[table_size];
    if (!bInited) { // init
        char c;
        FILE *pfile = fopen("t_0.95_quantiles.csv", "r");
        do { c = getc(pfile); } while (c != '\n'); // skip first line
        for (int i=0; i < table_size; i++)
            fscanf(pfile, "%lg", &(qtable[i]));
        fclose(pfile);
        bInited = 1;
    }
    if (P != 0.95) {
        printf("Error: P must be 0.95 in qt(). Exiting.\n\n");
        exit(0);
    }
    if (ndf > table_size - 1) {
        return(1.644854 * (1 + 0.9272142 / ndf));
    }
    else {
        return qtable[ndf];
    }
} // End qt

//-----
// Simulate BE for one trial
void BE_for_1_trial(double *radius_ref, double *radius_test, int *arm_size,
                    int *BE)
{
    double GMR_slope      = NormalRandom(GMR_slope_mean, GMR_slope_SE);
    double GMR_intercept = NormalRandom(GMR_intercept_mean, GMR_intercept_SE);
    double logGMR = log(GMR_slope * log(*radius_test) + GMR_intercept);

    double Var_slope_ref      = NormalRandom(Var_slope_mean,
                                             Var_slope_SE);
    double Var_intercept_ref = NormalRandom(Var_intercept_mean,
                                             Var_intercept_SE);
    double logVar_ref = exp(Var_slope_ref * *radius_ref + Var_intercept_ref);

```

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```

double Var_slope_test      = NormalRandom(Var_slope_mean,
                                           Var_slope_SE);
double Var_intercept_test = NormalRandom(Var_intercept_mean,
                                           Var_intercept_SE);
double logVar_test = exp(Var_slope_test * *radius_test + Var_intercept_test);

double logVar = logVar_ref + logVar_test;

double scaled_SD = sqrt(logVar / *arm_size);
double alogGMR   = NormalRandom(logGMR, scaled_SD);
double delta     = qt(0.95, 2*(*arm_size) - 2) * scaled_SD;
double CL_lo     = alogGMR - delta;
double CL_up     = alogGMR + delta;

*BE = (exp(CL_lo) > 0.8) && (exp(CL_up) < 1.25); // true or false...
} // End BE_for_1_trial

```

```

//-----
// Simulate power of N trials
void Power_of_N_trials(double *radius_ref, double *radius_test, int *arm_size,
                      int *N_trials, double *power)
{
    int i;

    double GMR_slope;
    double GMR_intercept;
    double logGMR;
    double Var_slope_ref;
    double Var_intercept_ref;
    double logVar_ref;
    double Var_slope_test;
    double Var_intercept_test;
    double logVar_test;
    double logVar;
    double scaled_SD;
    double alogGMR;
    double delta;
    double CL_lo;
    double CL_up;
    double BE;
    double cumBE = 0;

    for (i = 0; i < *N_trials; i++) {
        GMR_slope      = NormalRandom(GMR_slope_mean, GMR_slope_SE);
        GMR_intercept = NormalRandom(GMR_intercept_mean, GMR_intercept_SE);
        logGMR = log(GMR_slope * log(*radius_test) + GMR_intercept);

        Var_slope_ref      = NormalRandom(Var_slope_mean, Var_slope_SE);
        Var_intercept_ref = NormalRandom(Var_intercept_mean, Var_intercept_SE);
        logVar_ref = exp(Var_slope_ref * (*radius_ref) + Var_intercept_ref);

        Var_slope_test      = NormalRandom(Var_slope_mean, Var_slope_SE);
        Var_intercept_test = NormalRandom(Var_intercept_mean, Var_intercept_SE);
        logVar_test = exp(Var_slope_test * (*radius_test) + Var_intercept_test);

        logVar = logVar_ref + logVar_test;

        scaled_SD = sqrt(logVar / *arm_size);
        alogGMR   = NormalRandom(logGMR, scaled_SD);
        delta     = qt(0.95, 2 * (*arm_size) - 2) * scaled_SD;
        CL_lo     = alogGMR - delta;
        CL_up     = alogGMR + delta;

        BE = (exp(CL_lo) > 0.8) && (exp(CL_up) < 1.25); // true or false...
        cumBE = cumBE + BE;
    } // for i
}

```

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```

    *power = cumBE / *N_trials;
} // End Power_of_N_trials

//-----
// Simulate integrated (over mean drug particle radius) power of N trials
void Integrated_power_of_N_trials(double *radius_ref,
                                double *radius_test,
                                double *radius_sdlog,
                                int     *N_radii,
                                int     *arm_size,
                                int     *N_trials,
                                double *ipower)
{
    register int i, j;

    double radius_t;
    double GMR_slope;
    double GMR_intercept;
    double logGMR;
    double Var_slope_ref;
    double Var_intercept_ref;
    double logVar_ref;
    double Var_slope_test;
    double Var_intercept_test;
    double logVar_test;
    double logVar;
    double scaled_SD;
    double alogGMR;
    double delta;
    double CL_lo;
    double CL_up;
    double BE;
    double cumBE;

    *ipower = 0; // initialize

    for (j = 0; j < *N_radii; j++) {
        cumBE = 0; // re-initialize
        radius_t = LogNormalRandom(log(*radius_test), *radius_sdlog);
        for (i = 0; i < *N_trials; i++) {
            GMR_slope = NormalRandom(GMR_slope_mean, GMR_slope_SE);
            GMR_intercept = NormalRandom(GMR_intercept_mean, GMR_intercept_SE);
            logGMR = log(GMR_slope * log(radius_t) + GMR_intercept);

            Var_slope_ref = NormalRandom(Var_slope_mean, Var_slope_SE);
            Var_intercept_ref = NormalRandom(Var_intercept_mean, Var_intercept_SE);
            logVar_ref = exp(Var_slope_ref * (*radius_ref) + Var_intercept_ref);

            Var_slope_test = NormalRandom(Var_slope_mean, Var_slope_SE);
            Var_intercept_test = NormalRandom(Var_intercept_mean, Var_intercept_SE);
            logVar_test = exp(Var_slope_test * radius_t + Var_intercept_test);

            logVar = logVar_ref + logVar_test;

            scaled_SD = sqrt(logVar / *arm_size);
            alogGMR = NormalRandom(logGMR, scaled_SD);
            delta = qt(0.95, 2*(*arm_size) - 2) * scaled_SD;
            CL_lo = alogGMR - delta;
            CL_up = alogGMR + delta;

            BE = (exp(CL_lo) > 0.8) && (exp(CL_up) < 1.25); // true or false...
            cumBE = cumBE + BE;
        } // for i

        *ipower = *ipower + cumBE / *N_trials;
    }
}

```

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```
} // for j
*ipower = *ipower / *N_radii;
} // End Integrated_power_of_N_trials

// End

Meta-model power using C V1.R

## Calculate power of VBE trials, using a meta-model coded in C.
## V1: Use the regression meta-model obtained by sensitivity analysis.

IDtag = "_V1"

model.name = paste0("Meta-model_power_C_code", IDtag)

## Flag to save results
bsave = TRUE

## jump directly to dyn.load if the C library is already compiled

## otherwise:
dyn.unload(paste0(model.name, .Platform$dynlib.ext))

## Paths in C_call must be adapted to your machine
C_call = paste("C:/rtools43/x86_64-w64-mingw32.static.posix/bin/gcc",
              "-I\"C:\\Program Files\\R\\R-4.3.2\\include\"",
              "-DNDEBUG -DRFUN -Ofast -Wall -std=gnu99 -mfpmath=sse",
              "-msse2 -mstackrealign")

system(paste0(C_call, " -c ", model.name, ".c -o ", model.name, ".o"))

## Link - Path must be adapted
system(paste0("C:/rtools43/x86_64-w64-mingw32.static.posix/bin/gcc ",
            "-shared -s -static-libgcc ",
            "-o", model.name, ".dll ", model.name, ".o ",
            "-L\"C:\\Program Files\\R\\R-4.3.2\\bin\\x64 -lR"))

## load library
dyn.load(paste0(model.name, .Platform$dynlib.ext))

## Import radii
radius.sizes = read.csv(paste0("Sensitivity_analysis/data/",
                              "with measurement error/",
                              "Cmax_AUC_log_stats_df.csv"))$radius_sizes

## =====
## Comparison plot with PBPK results
if (bsave) {
  fname = paste0("Power_analysis/Power comparison using C", IDtag, ".pdf")
  pdf(fname)
}
##
N.subjects.v = 500 # maximum number of virtual subjects per arm

mycols = c("#000000", "#E69F00", "#56B4E9", "#009E73",
           "#F0E442", "#CC79A7", "#0072B2")

##-----
## Initialisation of the C outputs
power = c(0.0)
N.trials = 1000
Max.subj = 500
power_C = function(radius) {
  power.C = rep(NA, Max.subj)
```

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```

for (N.subj in 2:Max.subj) {
  out=.C("Power_of_N_trials",
        radius_ref = radius.sizes[1],
        radius_test = radius,
        arm_size   = as.integer(N.subj),
        N_trials   = as.integer(N.trials),
        power      = as.double(power))
  power.C[N.subj] = out$power
}
return(power.C)
}
##-----
radius = radius.sizes[1] # reference BE
## Plot V3 power estimate for BE test product
load(paste0("../Paliperidone workflow V3 (power)/Power_analysis/data/",
            "Cmax_power radius 4.6357 scrambled N=40K.Rsave"))
plot(2:N.subjects.v, power[-1], type="l",
     xlab="Number of subjects per arm",
     ylab="Probability of declaring bioequivalence", xlim=c(1,N.subjects.v),
     ylim=c(0, 1), col="grey", lwd=0.5, las=1)
##
ref.power = power_C(radius= radius)
## plot
lines(2:Max.subj, ref.power[-1], type="l", col=mycols[1], lwd=0.5, las=1)
## smooth:
lines(2:Max.subj, supsmu(2:Max.subj, ref.power[-1]))$y, lwd=2, col=mycols[1])
##
##-----
radius = 5.0679
## Plot V3 power estimate
load(paste0("../Paliperidone workflow V3 (power)/Power_analysis/data/",
            "Cmax_power radius 5.0679 N=40K.Rsave"))
lines(2:N.subjects.v, power[-1], type="l", col="grey", lwd=0.5, las=1)
##
ref.power = power_C(radius= radius)
## plot
lines(2:Max.subj, ref.power[-1], type="l", col=mycols[2], lwd=0.5, las=1)
## smooth:
lines(2:Max.subj, supsmu(2:Max.subj, ref.power[-1]))$y, lwd=2, col=mycols[2])
##
##-----
radius = 5.5000
## Plot V3 power estimate
load(paste0("../Paliperidone workflow V3 (power)/Power_analysis/data/",
            "Cmax_power radius 5.5000 N=40K.Rsave"))
lines(2:N.subjects.v, power[-1], type="l", col="grey", lwd=0.5, las=1)
##
ref.power = power_C(radius= radius)
## plot
lines(2:Max.subj, ref.power[-1], type="l", col=mycols[3], lwd=0.5, las=1)
## smooth:
lines(2:Max.subj, supsmu(2:Max.subj, ref.power[-1]))$y, lwd=2, col=mycols[3])
##
##-----
radius = 6.4500
## Plot V3 power estimate
load(paste0("../Paliperidone workflow V3 (power)/Power_analysis/data/",
            "Cmax_power radius 6.4500 N=100K.Rsave"))
lines(2:N.subjects.v, power[-1], type="l", col="grey", lwd=0.5, las=1)
##
ref.power = power_C(radius= radius)
## plot
lines(2:Max.subj, ref.power[-1], type="l", col=mycols[4], lwd=0.5, las=1)
## smooth:
lines(2:Max.subj, supsmu(2:Max.subj, ref.power[-1]))$y, lwd=2, col=mycols[4])
##
##-----
radius = 7.5000

```

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```
## Plot V3 power estimate
load(paste0("../Paliperidone workflow V3 (power)/Power_analysis/data/",
            "Cmax_power radius 7.5000 N=20K.Rsave"))
lines(2:N.subjects.v, power[-1], type="l", col="grey", lwd=0.5, las=1)
##
ref.power = power_C(radius= radius)
## plot
lines(2:Max.subj, ref.power[-1], type="l", col=mycols[5], lwd=0.5, las=1)
## smooth:
lines(2:Max.subj, supsmu(2:Max.subj, ref.power[-1])$y, lwd=2, col=mycols[5])
##
## Add legend
legend(x=375, y=0.55, cex=0.8,
      leg=c(expression(paste("4.6357 ", mu, "m *")),
            expression(paste("5.0679 ", mu, "m")),
            expression(paste("5.5 ", mu, "m")),
            expression(paste("6.45 ", mu, "m")),
            expression(paste("7.5 ", mu, "m"))), lty=1,
      col=c(mycols[1:5]), bty="o", bg="white", box.lty=0)
if (bsave) dev.off()

## End.
```

Compute meta-model integrated power using C V1.R

```
## Calculate integrated power of VBE trials, using a meta-model coded in C.
## V1: Use the regression meta-model obtained by sensitivity analysis.
```

```
IDtag = "_V1"
```

```
model.name = paste0("Meta-model_power_C_code", IDtag)
lib.name = paste0(model.name, .Platform$dynlib.ext)
```

```
dyn.load(lib.name)
```

```
## Import radii
radius.sizes = read.csv(paste0("Sensitivity_analysis/data/",
                              "With measurement error/",
                              "Cmax_AUC_log_stats_df.csv"))$radius_sizes
```

```
## =====
## Compute integrated power with different test radius uncertainties
```

```
## do for perfect BE
radius.geomean = radius.sizes[1] # reference formulation
Max.subj = 100000
N.radii = 5000 ## affects precision the most
N.trials = 500 ## affects precision the least
## compute at those sdlog values:
my.SDlogs = seq(0, 0.5, 0.1)
N.SDlogs = length(my.SDlogs)
my.cols = heat.colors(N.SDlogs, rev=T) # rainbow(N.SDlogs)
## compute only at those arm sizes:
from = 2
inc = (log(Max.subj) - log(from)) / 60
my.Nsubjs = exp(seq(log(from), log(Max.subj), inc))
## initialize
integ_power.C = matrix(NA, nrow=N.SDlogs, ncol=length(my.Nsubjs))
for (i in 1:length(my.SDlogs)) {
  ##
  ## Initialise C function outputs
  ipower = c(0.0)
  ## loop over arm sizes
  for (j in 1:length(my.Nsubjs)) {
    out=.C("Integrated_power_of_N_trials",
          radius_ref = radius.sizes[1],
          radius_test = radius.geomean,
```

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```
        radius_sdlog = my.SDlogs[i],
        N_radii      = as.integer(N.radii),
        arm_size     = as.integer(my.Nsubjs[j]),
        N_trials     = as.integer(N.trials),
        ipower       = as.double(ipower))
    integ_power.C[i,j] = out$ipower
  }
}
## save
fname = paste0("Integrated power/IP test radius=",
              format(radius.geomean, nsmall=4), ".Rsave")
save(list=c("radius.sizes", "radius.geomean", "my.SDlogs", "Max.subj",
           "N.radii", "my.Nsubjs", "N.trials", "integ_power.C"),
     file=fname)

## do at radius 5.500
radius.geomean = radius.sizes[9] # radius 5.5000
## initialize
integ_power.C = matrix(NA, nrow=N.SDlogs, ncol=length(my.Nsubjs))
for (i in 1:length(my.SDlogs)) {
  ## Initialise C function outputs
  ipower = c(0.0)
  ## loop over arm sizes
  for (j in 1:length(my.Nsubjs)) {
    out=.C("Integrated_power_of_N_trials",
          radius_ref = radius.sizes[1],
          radius_test = radius.geomean,
          radius_sdlog = my.SDlogs[i],
          N_radii      = as.integer(N.radii),
          arm_size     = as.integer(my.Nsubjs[j]),
          N_trials     = as.integer(N.trials),
          ipower       = as.double(ipower))
    integ_power.C[i,j] = out$ipower
  }
}
## save
fname = paste0("Integrated power/IP test radius=",
              format(radius.geomean, nsmall=4), ".Rsave")
save(list=c("radius.sizes", "radius.geomean", "my.SDlogs", "Max.subj",
           "N.radii", "my.Nsubjs", "N.trials", "integ_power.C"),
     file=fname)

## End.
```

Plot integrated power using C V1.R

```
## Plot integrated power of VBE trials, using a meta-model coded in C.

IDtag = "_V1"

## Import radii
radius.sizes = read.csv(paste0("Sensitivity_analysis/data/",
                              "With measurement error/",
                              "Cmax_AUC_log_stats_df.csv"))$radius_sizes

## Import GMR model calibration results
load(file=paste0("Sensitivity_analysis/data/",
                "With measurement error/Best Cmax GMR model.Rsave"))
tmp = summary(model)$coefficients
GMR_intercept_mean = tmp[1,1]
GMR_slope_mean     = tmp[2,1]
GMR_intercept_SE   = tmp[1,2]
GMR_slope_SE       = tmp[2,2]

## Import log Var model calibration results
load(file=paste0("Sensitivity_analysis/data/With measurement error/",
                "Best Cmax GMR log Var model_V3.Rsave"))
```

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```
tmp = summary(model)$coefficients
Var_intercept_mean = tmp[1,1]
Var_slope_mean     = tmp[2,1]
Var_intercept_SE   = tmp[1,2]
Var_slope_SE       = tmp[2,2]

## -----
## Function to simulate for 1 trial random true log(GMR) and
## pooled log(Cmax) variance
meta_model.Cmax = function (radius) {
  ref.radius = 4.6357
  GMR = GMR_slope_mean * log(radius) + GMR_intercept_mean
  ## population variance of log(Cmax) differences =
  ## variance test + variance ref
  logVar = exp(Var_slope_mean * radius      + Var_intercept_mean) +
            exp(Var_slope_mean * ref.radius + Var_intercept_mean)
  ##
  return(cbind(logGMR=log(GMR),logVar))
}

## =====
## plot integrated power for reference radius and radius 5.5 microm
for (k in c(1,9)) {
  radius.geomean = radius.sizes[k]
  ## load computations
  fname = paste0("Integrated power/IP test radius=",
                 format(radius.geomean, nsmall=4),".Rsave")
  load(file=fname)
  N.SDlogs = length(my.SDlogs)
  ##
  fname = paste0("Integrated power/IP test radius=",
                 format(radius.geomean, nsmall=4),".pdf")
  pdf(fname)
  my.cols = heat.colors(N.SDlogs, rev=T) # rainbow(N.SDlogs)
  plot(c(2,Max.subj), 0:1, type="n",
       xlab="Number of subjects per arm",
       ylab="Integrated probability of declaring bioequivalence",
       xlim=c(1,Max.subj),
       ylim=c(0, 1), col="grey", lwd=0.5, las=1)
  for (i in 1:length(my.SDlogs)) {
    lines(my.Nsubjs, integ_power.C[i,], type="l",
          col="grey", lwd=1, las=1)
    ## smooth:
    lines(my.Nsubjs, supsmu(my.Nsubjs, integ_power.C[i,])$y,
          lwd=2, col=my.cols[i])
    ## add theoretical probability of declaring BE
    meta = meta_model.Cmax(radius.sizes[k])
    GMRmeta.mean = meta[1] ## is log means difference
    tmp1 = abs(meta_model.Cmax(exp(log(radius.sizes[k]) - my.SDlogs[i]))[1] -
               GMRmeta.mean)
    tmp2 = abs(meta_model.Cmax(exp(log(radius.sizes[k]) + my.SDlogs[i]))[1] -
               GMRmeta.mean)
    proba = pnorm(q=log(1.25), mean=GMRmeta.mean, sd=tmp2) -
            pnorm(q=log(0.80), mean=GMRmeta.mean, sd=tmp1)
    points(max(my.Nsubjs), proba, cex=3, col=my.cols[i], pch=3)
    points(max(my.Nsubjs), proba, cex=2, col=my.cols[i], pch=20)
    ## O'Hagan
    ## lines(n1, gamma[,i]) # about OK
  }
  dev.off()
}

## End.
```

Meta-model safe-space V1.R

```
## A script to plot safe space with integrated power estimates
## V1: Use the regression meta-model obtained by sensitivity analysis
```

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```
IDtag = "_V1" # version number

## load library
model.name = paste0("Meta-model_power_C_code", IDtag)
lib.name    = paste0(model.name, ".Platform$dynlib.ext")
dyn.load(lib.name)

## =====
## Plot safe-space of log(radius) overlaid with power at size 200

## Load power calculations dataframe
load(file="Safe_space/data/Power at 200 dataframe.Rsave")

## Import model calibration results
load(file=paste0("Sensitivity_analysis/data/",
                "With measurement error/Best Cmax GMR model.Rsave"))

## Read stats for group sizes
metric_df_ratios = read.csv(paste0("Sensitivity_analysis/data/",
                                   "With measurement error/",
                                   "Cmax_AUC_GMR_stats_df.csv"))
metric_df_raw = read.csv(paste0("Sensitivity_analysis/data/",
                                 "With measurement error/",
                                 "Cmax_AUC_log_stats_df.csv"))

## By the way:
sum(metric_df_raw$group_sizes)
## gives a total of 552500 subjects simulated...

## This could be used to give an idea of precision
sqrt(pwr_200_df$Res) # mean squared diff between powers and smoothers

## Compute integrated power (can be skipped if already done)
## Compute at those sdlog values:
my.SDlogs = seq(0.05, 0.2, 0.05)
N.SDlogs  = length(my.SDlogs)
Max.subj  = 100000
my.Nsubjs = Max.subj
N.radii   = 5000 ## affects precision the most
N.trials  = 500  ## affects precision the least
## Compute for those mean radii
N.mean.radii = 100
mean.radii = seq(min(pwr_200_df$Radius), max(pwr_200_df$Radius),
                 length=N.mean.radii)

## Initialize
integ_power.C = matrix(NA, nrow=N.SDlogs, ncol=N.mean.radii)
## Loop for computations
for (j in 1:N.SDlogs) {
  ## Initialise C function outputs
  for (k in 1:N.mean.radii) {
    radius.geomean = mean.radii[k]
    ipower = c(0.0)
    out=.C("Integrated_power_of_N_trials",
           radius_ref = pwr_200_df$Radius[6],
           radius_test = radius.geomean,
           radius_sdlog = my.SDlogs[j],
           N_radii      = as.integer(N.radii),
           arm_size     = as.integer(my.Nsubjs),
           N_trials     = as.integer(N.trials),
           ipower       = as.double(ipower))
    integ_power.C[j,k] = out$ipower
  } # end for k
} # end for j
## 10 minutes
save(list=c("integ_power.C", "Max.subj", "N.radii", "N.trials",
           "my.SDlogs", "mean.radii"),
     file="Safe_space/data/Integrated Power for safe-space.Rsave")
```

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```
## load(file="Safe_space/data/Integrated Power for safe-space.Rsave")

## Plot power and integrated power:
N.SDlogs = length(my.SDlogs)
pdf("Safe_space/graphs/Integrated power vs. radius.pdf")
x = pwr_200_df$Radius
P = pwr_200_df$Power
w = metric_df_ratios$CmaxR_logvars # for correct weights
plot(x, P, type="n", las=1, log="x", cex=0.01/sqrt(w),
      ylab="", ylim=0:1,
      xlab=expression(paste("Mean particle radius (", mu, "m)")))
mtext(expression("Probability of declaring bioequivalence"), side=2, line=2.7)
## Manage ourselves the hatching that R does not know how to do!
usr <- par("usr")
## Left non-BE region
clip(1, cmax_x_upper, usr[3], usr[4])
for (i in seq(-1.8, 0.5, 0.075)) {
  abline(i, 2, col="red")
}
clip(1, 9, usr[3], usr[4])
abline(v=cmax_x_upper, col="red")
## Right non-BE region
clip(cmax_x_lower, 9, usr[3], usr[4])
for (i in seq(-1.8, 0.5, 0.075)) {
  abline(i, 2, col="red")
}
clip(1, 9, usr[3], usr[4])
abline(v=cmax_x_lower, col="red")
x1 = c(seq(min(x), 5.5, 0.01))
mysd1 = 0.79
y1 = dnorm(x1, 4.6357, mysd1)
lines(x1, y1 * max(P) / max(y1), col="grey", lwd=2)
myhinge = (y1 * max(P) / max(y1))[length(x1)]
## plot second part of ad hoc smoother
x2 = seq(5.5, max(x), 0.01)
mysd2 = 0.94
y2 = dnorm(x2, 4.6357, mysd2)
lines(x2, y2 * myhinge / max(y2), col="grey", lwd=2)
abline(h=c(0.05, 0.5, 0.90), lty=3)
## Loop to plot integrated power estimates
my.lty = c(1, 6, 5, 4)
for (j in 1:N.SDlogs) {
  lines(mean.radii, integ_power.C[j,], lty=my.lty[j], lwd=2, col="darkviolet")
  text(8, integ_power.C[j,length(mean.radii)],
       format(my.SDlogs[j], nsmall=2), adj=0, col="darkviolet")
} # end for j
dev.off()

## End.
```

Bayesian posterior with C meta-model.R

```
## Compute and plot the posterior GMR distribution, using a meta-model
## coded in C.

IDtag = "_v1"

## Import radii
radius.sizes = read.csv(paste0("Sensitivity_analysis/data/",
                               "With measurement error/",
                               "Cmax_AUC_log_stats_df.csv"))$radius_sizes

## Import GMR model calibration results
load(file=paste0("Sensitivity_analysis/data/",
                "With measurement error/Best Cmax GMR model.Rsave"))
tmp = summary(model)$coefficients
GMR_intercept_mean = tmp[1,1]
```

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```

GMR_slope_mean      = tmp[2,1]
GMR_intercept_SE    = tmp[1,2]
GMR_slope_SE        = tmp[2,2]

## Import log Var model calibration results
load(file=paste0("Sensitivity_analysis/data/With measurement error/",
                "Best Cmax GMR log Var model_V3.Rsave"))
tmp = summary(model)$coefficients
Var_intercept_mean = tmp[1,1]
Var_slope_mean     = tmp[2,1]
Var_intercept_SE   = tmp[1,2]
Var_slope_SE       = tmp[2,2]

## -----
## Function to simulate for 1 trial random true log(GMR) and
## pooled log(Cmax) variance
meta_model.Cmax = function (radius) {
  ref.radius = 4.6357
  GMR = GMR_slope_mean * log(radius) + GMR_intercept_mean
  ## population variance of log(Cmax) differences =
  ## variance test + variance ref
  logVar = exp(Var_slope_mean * radius      + Var_intercept_mean) +
            exp(Var_slope_mean * ref.radius + Var_intercept_mean)
  ##
  return(cbind(logGMR=log(GMR), logVar))
}
tmp = meta_model.Cmax(radius.sizes[1])
tmp

## =====
## plot posterior GMR for reference radius and radius 5.5 microm
my.SDlogs = seq(0, 0.5, 0.1)
N.SDlogs  = length(my.SDlogs)
N.samples = 10000

for (k in c(1,9)) {
  radius.geomean = radius.sizes[k]
  ## load integrated power computations
  fname = paste0("Integrated power/IP test radius=",
                format(radius.geomean, nsmall=4), ".Rsave")
  load(file=fname)
  ## plot name
  fname = paste0("Bayesian posteriors/Posterior test radius=",
                format(radius.geomean, nsmall=4), ".pdf")
  pdf(fname)
  par(mfrow=c(3,2), mar=c(2.9,0.1,0.2,0.5))
  for (j in 2:N.SDlogs) {
    ## compute
    radius_t = rlnorm(N.samples, meanlog=log(radius.sizes[k]),
                    sdlog=my.SDlogs[j]);
    GMRmeta.mean = rep(NA, N.samples)
    for (i in 1:N.samples) {
      meta = meta_model.Cmax(radius_t[i])
      GMRmeta.mean[i] = exp(meta[1]) ## GMRs
    }
    ## plot histogram
    tmp = hist(GMRmeta.mean, breaks=20, plot=F)
    my.max = max(tmp$density)
    plot(tmp, freq=F, yaxt="n", main="", xlab="GMR", ylab="",
         xlim=c(0, 2), ylim=c(0, my.max), lty=1, border="lightgrey", col=NULL)
    ## plot fitted normal
    tmp.mean = mean(GMRmeta.mean, na.rm=T)
    tmp.sd   = sd(GMRmeta.mean, na.rm=T)
    my.x = seq(0,2,0.01)
    lines(my.x, dnorm(my.x, tmp.mean, tmp.sd), lwd=2)
    rect(0.00, 0, 0.80, my.max * 0.8, dens=6, col="red")
    rect(1.25, 0, 2.00, my.max * 0.8, dens=6, col="red")
    proba.BE = 1 - (length(which(GMRmeta.mean < 0.80)) +

```

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```
                length(which(GMRmeta.mean > 1.25))) / N.samples
text(0.05, my.max * 0.87, paste0("log SD = ", format(my.SDlogs[j], dig=2)),
     adj=0, cex=1.5)
text(1.3, my.max * 0.95, paste0("P BE post = ", format(proba.BE, dig=2)),
     adj=0)
##
## paste integrated power computations asymptote
proba.IP = integ_power.C[j,dim(integ_power.C)[2]]
text(1.3, my.max * 0.87, paste0("P BE IP      = ",
                                format(proba.IP, dig=2)), adj=0)
} # end for j SDlogs
dev.off()
} # end for k

## End.
```